

FACTORS INFLUENCING CHILDREN'S SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information about meaning of speech and the biological and environmental factors such as social contact and socioeconomic status that children's development of English speech. In order to promote successful language acquisition, it also discusses problems like mental health concerns and present cutting-edge methods like technology-assisted learning and individualized techniques.

I. INTRODUCTION

Language and speech are vital communication tools that allow people to exchange ideas, express emotions and share their thoughts. Language serves as a medium for dialogue. This method of verbal communication is essential for human expression and comprehension. In ancient times, the concept of speech was based on many philosophical and cultural approaches. Each culture had different views about the purpose of speech, its role and social importance. The idea of speech occupied a central place in ancient Greek philosophy. Aristotle defined speech as the art of persuasion. He saw the study of speech as a means of influencing people's feelings, thoughts and decisions [1]. However, over time, concepts lost their meaning and acquired new contexts. In the modern world, speech is often understood a multifaceted phenomenon. It goes beyond communicating ideas to include social, psychological and cognitive elements.

As a person grows up, his speech develops through various influences from childhood. Speech is an integral part of child development. The formation of a child's speech develops depending on the environment, education, family and other factors. For example, the influence of the child's environment and the language environment in the family is great. If a child has a family that speaks many languages, he can learn more languages quickly. In addition, the child's interaction with the teacher or tutor also affects his speech. Therefore, children's English learning process is influenced by many of the above factors and these factors cover various areas from the age of the child to teaching methods.

II. METHODS

During learning English language, it is understood that the development of children's speech is shaped by the interplay of biological, social, psychological and environmental factors which collectively influence their communication skills. For instance, a child living in an English-

speaking country with educational resources such as books, media and interactive tools will have more opportunities to practice and improve their language skills. However, children learning English as a second language happens when a child or student choose to study English at school and then learns the syntax and structure of the language as well as the correctness of their mistakes [2]. Moreover, in Uzbekistan the development of English language is greatly influenced by schools and colleges. Many educational institutions require students to take English and some emphasize vocabulary and grammar while offering more real-world speaking opportunities through group projects and talks. Another the most important factor is in the early development of human conversation has been identified as the social setting [3]. Through their interactions with peers, caretakers and members of their community, children are exposed to language in social contexts. Children gain knowledge of vocabulary, syntax and pragmatics through these encounters. Research indicates that variations in infant language development are linked to socioeconomic level (SES) variances [4]. SES affects not just vocabulary growth but also grammatical development, narrative skills, phonological awareness and language processing speed [5]. Because, families with higher socioeconomic status typically have more time and educational background to spend meaningful verbal interactions with their children as well as more access to books, educational toys and stimulating activities that promote language development. Moreover, a number of biological elements that can affect how children's speech develops as they learn English. These elements shape children's capacity to successfully learn new languages by laying the groundwork for how they develop and use voice and language. According Damasio and Damasio (1992) that the brain processes and produces language through three interrelated sets of components. For instance, a vast array of brain networks in both the left and right hemispheres handle non-verbal communication between the body and its surroundings. A person's sensory and motor systems process everything they do, see, think or feel while acting in the world which connects these encounters [6].

III. RESULTS

The result of this study demonstrates the interconnected effects of environmental, social, biological and educational factors, highlighting the complex aspects that influence children's English speech development. The findings, highlight that while exposure to an environment that is rich in English and a crucial factor in language development, peer interactions and socioeconomic status (SES) are also pivotal factors. Despite the fact that children from low-SES households usually have parents with poor incomes, educational attainments of professional status, studies indicate that maternal education is the primary and most significant factor in predicting children's language development [7]. A child's capacity to acquire a language, particularly English, can be strongly impacted by their physical and mental well-being. A child's ability to study can be hampered by illnesses or mental health conditions, even if they have access to top-notch educational tools. Children who suffer from mental health conditions like depression or stress may find it difficult to focus and experience difficulties learning both their native language and the national English language.

IV. DISCUSSION

While a child's speech may be influenced by a number of things, social media is also a significant component in a current world when it comes to language development, both in English and other languages. Constant engagement with parents, friends. Even social media may not have any effect at all or have very little effect, if a child's speech issues are caused by their health or brain activity. Consequently, the first step for each youngster learning English at school is to overcome the language and speech restrictions. A child's speech development is significantly influenced by cognitive growth as well. For instance, taking schoolchildren. Their parents or other family members encourage them with various motivational phrases when

they achieve exceptional grades or results from educational activities and puzzles. This is a tradition in all countries, not just English families. In Uzbekistan, family members compliment a child who performs well by using terms like “excellent”, “honey” and “smart”. Similar to this, in an English-speaking setting, phrases like “great job”, “excellent” and “my baby” are encouraged. A child who hears these phrases frequently eventually develops them in his speech and employs them in social interactions [8]. When children begin studying English in school, they should gain a thorough understanding of syntax and morphology regardless of any other influences. During the English language learning process, they will also need to develop the habit of consistent practice. For instance, students can use the new English terms they are learning in their daily conversation or watch English-language cartoons daily to enhance their English speech and knowledge. A child can converse in English fearlessly if he has a thorough understanding of it. In addition, to their speech development issues, this helps them talk in front of the team with ease and relieves mental strain. Virtual reality environments, interactive storytelling, AI-powered language apps or exercising regularly with ChatGPT can immerse kids in rich, captivating language experiences that will speed up their acquisition of grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation. Learning becomes more engaging and effective through gamified language activities and cross-cultural interactions, which enhance speech development while deepening cultural understanding. Strategies like “parent-coaching programs,” which train caregivers to better model language, and “peer-assisted learning,” which involves youngsters learning together, have also demonstrated potential in improving speaking abilities.

V. CONCLUSION

Using both conventional and cutting-edge techniques, a diverse strategy is needed to improve kids’ English speech development. Even while environmental and biological elements are important, contemporary approaches like technology-assisted learning and individualized teaching methods might help this process even more. Learning can be made more fun and efficient by using gamified language exercises and cross-cultural interactions, which promote both speech development and a greater comprehension of other cultures.

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